

Examining the Impact of Historical Site Excursions on Students' Attitudes in Social Studies Education

Sosyal Bilgiler Eğitiminde Tarihi Mekan Gezilerinin Öğrencilerin Tutumlarına Etkisinin İncelenmesi

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ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın amacı, sosyal bilgiler dersi kapsamında tarihi mekan gezilerinin ilkököl 4. sınıf öğrencilerinin tutumlarına etkisini incelemektir. Çalışma, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden görüşme modeline dayalı olarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Mevcut araştırma 2024-2025 eğitim-öğretim yılında yapılmıştır. Araştırma gönüllü katılımlı çerçevesinde Diyarbakır İli/Ergani İlçe Milli Eğitim Müdürlüğüne bağlı iki devlet ilkokulunda öğrenim gören 30 öğrenci üzerinden yürütülmüştür. Tarihi mekan gezisi Diyarbakır/Ergani ilçesi sınırları içerisinde yer alan Çayönü Höyüğü ve Hilar Mağaralarına yapılmıştır. Gerçekleştirilen aktivitenin etkisini belirlemek üzere araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu kullanılmıştır. Aktivite sonrasında, yapılan geziyle ilgili 27 öğrenciyle görüşme yapılmıştır. Görüşme sonrasında elde edilen verilerin çözümlenmesinde betimsel analiz tekniğinden faydalanılmıştır. Mevcut araştırma sonucunda; sosyal bilgiler eğitimi kapsamında gerçekleştirilen tarihi mekan gezisinin “bilişsel”, “duygusal” ve “davranışsal” açıdan öğrencilerin tutumlarını olumlu etkilediği saptanmıştır. Diğer bir ifadeyle, öğrencilerin ilgili gezi sonrasında sosyal bilgiler dersine yönelik anlamlı öğrenmeler geliştirdikleri, olumlu duygu ve değerler oluşturdukları ve bunlara bağlı olarak olumlu davranış eğilimleri sergiledikleri saptanmıştır. Bu sonuçlardan hareketle; sosyal bilgiler dersine yönelik tarihi mekan gezilerinin etkin bir şekilde yapılması, mevcut çalışma konusunun farklı araştırma yöntemleri çerçevesinde ve farklı kademelerde de etkisinin incelenmesi gerektiği önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sosyal Bilgiler Eğitimi, Tarihi Mekan, Öğrenci, Tutum, Gezi

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of historical site excursions, conducted within the scope of the social studies education, on the attitudes of 4th grade primary school students. The study was carried out using a qualitative research design based on the interview model. The research was conducted during the 2024-2025 academic year. Within the framework of voluntary participation, the study was conducted with 30 students enrolled in two public primary schools affiliated with the Ergani District Directorate of National Education in Diyarbakır, Türkiye. The historical site excursions included the Çayönü Mound and Hilar Caves located within the boundaries of the Ergani district. A semi-structured interview form developed by the researchers was used to determine the effect of the activity. Following the activity, interviews were conducted with 27 students regarding their experience of the excursion. The data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using the descriptive analysis technique. The findings of the study revealed that the historical site excursion conducted as part of social studies education positively influenced students' attitudes in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions. In other words, the students demonstrated meaningful learning outcomes related to the social studies education, developed positive feelings and values, and exhibited favorable behavioral tendencies following the excursion. Based on these results, it is recommended that historical site excursions be implemented effectively in social studies instruction, and that the effects of such excursions be examined using different research methods and at various educational levels.

Keywords: Social Studies Education, Historical Site, Student, Attitude, Excursion

INTRODUCTION

The rapid changes in science and technology, the transformation occurring within the structure of society, and efforts to enhance the quality of education have led to significant shifts in educational paradigms, as in many other domains in today's world (Durnacı & Ültay, 2020). A key factor

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contributing to this transformation is the growing awareness of the limitations of traditional teaching methods, especially considering changing societal demands. Traditional education is characterized by a teacher-centered approach, an emphasis on theoretical knowledge, passive student involvement in teaching-learning activities, and limited levels of interactive learning (Çengelci, 2013). These core components of traditional pedagogy are increasingly viewed as insufficient in meeting the demands of contemporary constructivist educational models. In contrast to traditional approaches, constructivist pedagogy emphasizes the active participation of students throughout the entire learning process, their central role in the processing of knowledge, the alignment of educational content with the development of students' problem-solving skills, the real-life relevance of learning activities, and the prioritization of collaborative learning (Saraç, 2017; Yurdakul, 2008). This shift in instructional methods has also profoundly altered the perception of the concept of school. While traditional education confines teaching and learning activities largely within the boundaries of the school, contemporary educational perspectives advocate for learning experiences that are rooted in real life, closely connected to the natural environment, and inclusive of out-of-school educational practices (Durnacı & Ültay, 2020).

Out-of-school education refers to an instructional approach that involves conducting learning activities outside the conventional school environment, in settings such as historical and cultural sites, workplaces, parks, gardens, and forests (Burriss & Burriss, 2011). The primary goal of this approach is to support the curriculum by linking educational outcomes to real life contexts, thereby fostering meaningful and lasting learning (Sontay, Tutar & Karamustafaoğlu, 2016). The integration of theoretical knowledge with real-life experiences, along with experiential learning, allows students to address real-world problems more accurately and effectively, to approach topics from broader perspectives, to gain tangible experiences, to engage multiple senses, and to find learning activities more enjoyable (Çetinkaya, 2021; İnce & Akcanca, 2021). In this respect, the out-of-school education model aims to support students' holistic development cognitively, affectively, and behaviorally by focusing on the broad set of skills required in the 21st century (Gürültü, Aslan & Alcı, 2019; Gonzalez-Perez & Ramirez-Montoya, 2022).

One of the most significant advantages of out-of-school education practices is their overall positive impact on student attitudes, which plays a key role in enhancing the quality of teaching and learning processes (Turhan, Aydoğdu, Şensoy & Yıldırım, 2008). Attitude refers to the combination of feelings, thoughts, behaviors, tendencies, and beliefs either positive or negative developed by individuals toward a particular object, based on the knowledge and perspectives acquired through interaction with their environment (Wood & Wood, 1993). Attitudes not only facilitate individuals' adaptation to their environment but also possess latent power in shaping their perspectives, preferences, and behaviors. According to Olufemi (2012), the guiding and evaluative role is framed through three main dimensions: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. The coherence both within and among these components plays a crucial role in the formation of attitudes. This formation process manifests in various aspects of an individual's life and provides predictive insights into the quality of learning activities. Accordingly, a strong relationship exists between attitude and learning activities (Dikmen & Bahçecil, 2022). Attitude significantly contributes to the effectiveness of learning processes, enhances productivity related to the subject matter, supports retention of learned material, and enables individuals to maximize their potential in line with their motivation and effort (Dikmen & Bahçecil, 2022; Erdoğan, 2020).

Within the scope of out-of-school education, field excursions to historical sites hold particular importance in the instruction of social studies. This is especially evident in units where knowledge, skills, and behaviors related to culture and history are taught (Kabapınar, 2014). Attempting to teach historical content solely through textbooks can hinder students' active engagement, lead to abstraction of learning outcomes, and compromise the retention of knowledge (Ata, 2015; Rohlf, 2015; Stolare, Ludvigsson & Trenter, 2021). Therefore, field trips to historical sites play a critical role in helping students understand that history is not limited to theoretical knowledge, in recognizing the real life relevance of historical topics, and in comprehending the transformation of societies over time and its implications (Çulha Özbaş, 2015; Winch, 2013). Moreover, this model facilitates the concretization of historical content, fosters emotional connections with the past, and supports meaningful and lasting learning through observation and analysis skills. Accordingly, field trips to historical sites within the scope of out-of-school education are considered to play a supportive and complementary role in learning processes (Dinç & Öztemur, 2017; McKernan, 2018; Seidel & Hudson, 1999).

A review of the literature on historical site visits reveals that most of the relevant studies employ a descriptive survey model, are predominantly conducted with middle school students, and that there is a limited number of experimental or applied studies (Dinç & Öztemur, 2017). A noteworthy point is that despite students often living near or passing by historical sites, their level of awareness regarding these places remains low, and teachers rarely integrate such site visits into their instructional practices (Dinç, Erdil & Keçe, 2011; Aktın, Karakuş & Sağlam, 2013). Based on this information, a review of the literature showed that no applied study has yet been conducted to investigate how field trips to historical sites affect the attitudes of 4th grade primary school students. Therefore, the present study is considered important in terms of exploring students' views on historical site excursions, providing insights for future research in this area, and addressing a gap in the existing literature.

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of historical site excursions conducted within the context of the social studies education on the attitudes of 4th grade primary school students. In line with this purpose, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i) What are the views of 4th grade students regarding the “cognitive” dimension of attitude following historical site excursions conducted within the context of the social studies education?
- ii) What are the views of 4th grade students regarding the “affective” dimension of attitude following historical site excursions conducted within the context of the social studies education?
- iii) What are the views of 4th grade students regarding the “behavioral” dimension of attitude following historical site excursions conducted within the context of the social studies education?

METHOD

Research Design

This study was conducted using the qualitative interview method, one of the qualitative research designs. This method offers significant advantages for uncovering participants' attitudes and behaviors related to the research topic and is particularly suitable for examining the issue from a broad and in depth perspective (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). Therefore, it was deemed appropriate for the current study.

Study Group

To achieve the study's purpose, the participating schools were selected using the simple random sampling method. In this sampling technique, each unit in the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample (Arıkan, 2004). Accordingly, following consultations with school administrators, Yolbulan Primary School and Çakırfakir Primary School agreed to participate in the planned application based study within their means. The qualitative data related to the students participating in the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of Participating Students

Student Characteristics	Study Group		
	f	%	
Gender			
	Male	11	36,66
	Female	19	63,33
	Total	30	100

As shown in Table 1, of the total 30 participating students, 11 (36.66%) are male and 19 (63.33%) are female.

Implementation Process of Activities

In this study, which aims to determine 4th grade primary school students' attitudes toward historical site visits, permissions were obtained from Yolbulan and Çakırfakir Primary Schools in accordance with the study plan. The activities were implemented in May 2024, during the 2024–2025 academic year. Efforts were made to ensure the alignment of the historical site visits with the learning outcomes outlined in the curriculum. Following the implementation of the activities, 27 students voluntarily participated in interviews to assess their attitudes toward the historical site visits.

Data Collection Tools

To determine the attitudes of 4th grade students toward historical site excursions, a semi-structured interview form developed by the researchers was used. Expert opinions from the field were sought during the development of this form to ensure its validity and appropriateness.

Data Analysis

The data collected through the semi-structured interview form were analyzed using descriptive analysis techniques. This technique enables the identification of themes and concepts in participants’ responses, facilitates data comparison, and allows for a comprehensive and objective examination of the research topic. Additionally, direct quotations may be included to enhance the clarity and comprehensibility of the findings (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006; Namey, Guest, Thairu & Johnson, 2008).

FINDINGS

This section presents the analysis of the data collected from participants in line with the research objectives, along with the resulting findings and their interpretation.

i) What are the views of 4th grade primary school students regarding the “cognitive” dimension of attitude in relation to historical site excursions conducted as part of the social studies education? The findings related to this question are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Codes Identified within the Cognitive Dimension of Attitude

Theme / Category	Code	f	%
Cognitive	Knowledge	27	100
	Historical Empathy	17	62,96
	Exploration	24	88,88
	Understanding	27	100
	Association	22	81,48

Based on the analysis of student responses, the following codes were identified: “knowledge”, “historical empathy”, “exploration”, “understanding”, and “association”. Sample student statements include: “...I learned that they built tombs in the rocks for the people who had died...” (Knowledge-S24); “...I saw that people built small houses close to each other and had simple furniture. Life must have been simpler and more difficult back then...” (Historical Empathy-S3); “...I saw human drawings on the rocks. There are similarities and differences between the clothing styles of people then and now...” (Exploration-S3); “...I understood better how people lived in the past...” (Understanding-S8); “...Thanks to what I learned and saw during this trip, I understood the topics in the social studies class better...” (Association-S14).

According to Papanastasiou (2002), positive and negative attitudes in the cognitive domain are generally shaped by two main elements: beliefs and knowledge. That is, the level of knowledge one acquires about a certain event or situation, along with the beliefs developed accordingly, can influence one’s attitude positively or negatively. Based on this perspective and the findings of the current study, it can be concluded that the activity conducted during the historical site visit positively influenced students’ cognitive skills and, in turn, their attitudes toward the social studies education. These findings highlight the significance and educational value of the activity.

ii) What are the views of 4th grade primary school students regarding the “affective” dimension of attitude in relation to historical site excursions conducted as part of the social studies education? The findings related to this question are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Codes Identified within the Affective Dimension of Attitude

Theme / Category	Code	f	%
Affective	Motivation	25	92,59
	Enjoyment	24	88,88
	Encouragement	21	77,77
	Happiness	27	100
	Curiosity	18	66,66
	Appreciation	23	85,18
	Liking	27	100

Analysis of student responses revealed the following codes: “motivation”, “enjoyment”, “encouragement”, “happiness”, “curiosity”, “appreciation”, and “liking”. Examples of student comments include: “...I really enjoyed this trip. I also felt the excitement of seeing and learning new things...” (Motivation-S12); “...The trip was great. We had a lot of fun with our friends along the excursions...” (Enjoyment-S9); “...Some of our friends couldn’t join. I hope they get to see those places too...” (Encouragement-S21); “...I liked it a lot because it was my first time visiting ancient buildings...” (Happiness-S23); “...After what I experienced and saw on this trip, I really want to see Göbekli Tepe and other historical sites...” (Curiosity-S13); “...This trip really caught my interest. I think such trips are very important...” (Appreciation-S8); “...I really liked this trip, and I started to enjoy the social studies education more...” (Liking-S18).

According to Olufemi (2012), the affective component of attitude consists of the feelings and values associated with the attitude object. It plays a vital role in the formation and maintenance of attitude. When these insights are considered in conjunction with the findings of the present study, it can be concluded that the activity significantly influenced students’ emotional responses toward historical site visits in a positive manner.

iii) What are the views of 4th grade primary school students regarding the “behavioral” dimension of attitude in relation to historical site excursions conducted as part of the social studies education? The findings related to this question are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Codes Identified within the Behavioral Dimension of Attitude

Theme / Category	Code	f	%
Behavioral	Sharing	20	74,07
	Behavioral Intention	24	88,88
	Response	21	77,77
	Feedback	26	96,29
	Justification	27	100
	Action	14	51,85

The codes identified from student responses within the behavioral domain include: “sharing”, “behavioral intention”, “response”, “feedback”, “justification”, and “action”. Examples of relevant statements include: “...I told my family and friends about what I learned on this trip...” (Sharing-S15); “...I plan to join other historical site trips in the future...” (Behavioral Intention-S4); “...Since the trip, documentaries, images, and old buildings I pass by have caught my attention...” (Response-S7); “...Our teacher asked us about our thoughts on the trip, and we shared our impressions...” (Feedback-S15); “...I believe historical site excursions are very useful...” (Justification-S16); “...I really liked this trip. Afterward, I went to visit historical and natural places in Diyarbakır/Eğil with my family...” (Action-S17).

According to Haddock & Maio (2008), the behavioral dimension of attitude refers to the tendency to exhibit behaviors based on emotional and cognitive components, shaped by prior experiences. The findings from the current activity indicate that the historical site visit had a positive effect on students’ attitudes, which was reflected in their actual behaviors. Therefore, it can be stated that the activity was meaningful within the context of the social studies curriculum.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the historical site visit carried out within the scope of the social studies education, it was found that the activity positively influenced 4th grade students’ attitudes in a multidimensional manner cognitively, affectively, and behaviorally based on the codes and opinions obtained. Rahmet & Oruç (2024), in their study involving middle school students, concluded that historical site visits had a significant impact on students’ attitudes and academic achievement. Similarly, Bozok, Sevim, Küçük & Sevim (2022), in a study conducted as part of a nature based education project with high school students, found that historical site visits positively influenced students’ attitudes and awareness regarding cultural heritage. These findings are consistent with the general results of the present study.

When the findings are examined by theme, student responses within the cognitive dimension revealed codes such as “knowledge,” “historical empathy,” “exploration,” “understanding,” and “association.” A review of the relevant literature shows that historical site visits in the teaching of history related topics

contribute positively to students' historical understanding, empathy skills, academic performance, and retention of knowledge (Folaranmi, 2016; Gökkaya & Yeşilbursa, 2009; Harrison, 2012; Özü, 2010; Stolare, Ludvigsson & Trenter, 2021; Bartelds, Savenije & Van Boxtel, 2020; Ludvigsson, Stolare & Trenter, 2021). These results are consistent with the findings under the cognitive dimension of attitudes in the present study, highlighting the significance of historical site visits in facilitating meaningful learning in history related subjects within the social studies curriculum.

Within the affective dimension, student responses included codes such as "motivation," "enjoyment," "encouragement," "happiness," "curiosity," "valuing," and "appreciation." These codes demonstrate that the activity had a positive emotional impact on students' attitudes. Üztemur, Dinç & Acun (2018) found that historical site visits positively influenced students' emotions and increased their interest in the social studies education. Mitchell & Elwood (2012) concluded that extracurricular educational activities related to history increased students' willingness to learn about historical and cultural heritage. Rohlf (2015) noted that such out-of-school learning activities strengthened in class learning and made educational experiences more enjoyable. Savenije, Van Boxtel & Grever (2014) found that students considered heritage site visits valuable for understanding history related topics. Stolare, Ludvigsson & Trenter (2021) reported that historical site visits positively affected students emotionally and contributed to improved learning. These findings support the results obtained in the present study.

In the behavioral dimension, codes such as "telling/sharing," "behavioral intention/tendency," "showing reaction," "providing feedback," "advocacy," and "action" were identified through student responses. These findings suggest that the activity was behaviorally internalized by the students and positively reflected in their attitudes. Parrello & Valentine (2022) found that historical site visits had an impact on student behavior, noting that the majority of students shared their experiences with others, intended to participate in future excursions, advocated for the importance of such excursions, and responded to related questions. Similarly, Berg & Stolare (2024) concluded that historical site excursions positively influenced students' behavior with an emphasis on sharing experiences, behavioral intentions, and advocacy in students' statements. The findings of the present study are thus consistent with existing research in the literature.

In light of the results obtained from both the present study and previous studies in the literature, it is evident that historical site excursions should be effectively utilized in social studies education. Furthermore, in order to comprehensively examine the multifaceted impact of such excursions on student attitudes, it is recommended that future research be conducted across different educational levels and using diverse research methodologies.

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